

A STUDY ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE FOOD YARD PROGRAM (P2L) IN THE CITY OF MATARAM

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15846892>

Published Date: 10-April-2025, Amendment Date: 09-July-2025

Abstract: Food security is an important aspect of economic and social development in Indonesia (Fattah, 2006; Bukhtiarova, 2019). Mataram City faces challenges due to the conversion of agricultural land which has an impact on food production capacity (Sulityawati, 2014; Osly et al., 2020). The Sustainable Food Yard (P2L) Program is present as a solution by utilizing yard land to increase household food security and community empowerment (Rosyadi et al., 2022; Tama & Priyanti, 2022).

This study aims to analyze the implementation of the P2L program, identify obstacles in its implementation, and formulate strategies to optimize the sustainability of the program in Mataram City. The research method used is descriptive with a qualitative approach. The research location was selected by purposive sampling, namely in Pagesangan Timur, Pejeruk Abian, and Karang Taliwang Villages. The research informants consisted of three key informants and 18 informants from each target group. Data collection techniques include in-depth interviews, observation, and documentation. The research variables include the preparation stage, implementation, benefits, and program evaluation (Juknis P2L 2024).

The results of the study indicate that the implementation of the P2L Program in Mataram City has been running in accordance with the technical instructions set by the Ministry of Agriculture (2020). This program provides significant benefits for recipient groups in increasing access to fresh food, empowering household economies, and yard cultivation skills (Putri et al., 2021). However, there are several obstacles in its implementation, such as limited land, lack of ongoing technical assistance, and dependence on government assistance funds (Lidayya, 2016). Weather factors and pest attacks are also challenges that hinder yard productivity (Saputri, 2016). Based on these findings, it is recommended that local governments increase training for program participants, provide ongoing assistance, and encourage innovation in yard management to be more adaptive to environmental changes (Tama & Priyanti, 2022). In addition, there needs to be synergy with other empowerment programs to strengthen the sustainability of P2L in Mataram City (Mataram City Agriculture Service, 2023).

Keywords: Sustainable Food Yard, Program Implementation, Food Security, Mataram City.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is a sector that makes a major contribution to the Indonesian economy, especially in supporting national food security (Fattah, 2006). However, the increasing conversion of agricultural land is a serious challenge for food production, especially in urban areas such as Mataram City. This city is experiencing quite high land conversion, with the land area continuing to decrease from 1,497.26 ha in 2021 to 1,381.84 ha in 2023 due to changes in land use functions and non-rice field land data of 917.26 ha, this non-rice field land includes various types of uses, including yard land (Mataram City Agriculture Service, 2023).

One solution to overcome this problem is to utilize yard land as a source of food production. The Sustainable Food Yard Program (P2L) initiated by the Ministry of Agriculture in 2020 aims to increase the availability, accessibility, and utilization of food for households, as well as increase family income through market orientation (Tama & Priyanti, 2022). This program focuses on the utilization of yard land, idle land, and unproductive empty land to produce sustainable food. The implementation of P2L is part of the community empowerment strategy, especially through the Women Farmers Group (KWT). Until 2023, there are 66 KWTs that have benefited from this program. This program not only aims to increase food production, but also supports efforts to eradicate stunting and community-based food security (Rosyadi et al., 2022).

In Mataram City, the implementation of the P2L Program has involved various community groups, especially the Women Farmers Group (KWT), which has an important role in the management and utilization of yard land. However, in practice, there are various obstacles faced, such as limited land, lack of technical assistance, and limited access to production facilities and markets. Therefore, this study is important to understand the extent to which the implementation of the P2L Program in Mataram City has been running, what obstacles are faced, and what optimization strategies can be carried out to increase the effectiveness of this program.

However, the implementation of this program still faces various obstacles, both in terms of technical, environmental, mentoring, to limited knowledge and skills in managing yards. Therefore, a more in-depth study is needed to evaluate the implementation of this program, identify existing challenges, and formulate strategies that can improve the effectiveness and sustainability of P2L in Mataram City.

Problem Formulation Based on the background above, the formulation of the problem in this study is: 1. How is the implementation of the P2L Program in Mataram City? 2. What are the obstacles faced in the implementation of the P2L Program in Mataram City?. Research Objectives This study aims to 1. Find out the implementation of the P2L Program in Mataram City. 2. Find out the obstacles in the implementation of the P2L Program in Mataram City. Benefits of the Study The results of this study are expected to provide the following benefits: 1. Increase researchers' knowledge about the importance of factors that influence the sustainability of the P2L Program. 2. As information or material to improve the development of the P2L Program. 3. As information for other researchers who

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II. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive method. The research location was determined purposively in three sub-districts in Mataram City, namely Mataram, Ampenan, and Cakranegara Sub-districts. The research informants consisted of KWT administrators and members, agricultural extension workers, and other related parties who play a role in the implementation of the P2L program. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, field observations, and documentation studies. want to study the same problem.

Data analysis was conducted using a thematic approach, where the data obtained was categorized based on the main aspects of program implementation, such as the preparation stage, implementation, benefits, and obstacles faced. Data validation was carried out through triangulation of sources and methods. The research method used in this thesis is a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. This method aims to describe or explain a phenomenon based on data collected in depth. This study examines the status of a group of people, an object, a condition, a system of thought, or a class of events in the present.

Unit of Analysis

The unit of analysis in this study is the individual members of the Women Farmers Group (KWT) who are recipients of the Sustainable Food Yard (P2L) program and individual parties related to the implementation of the program in Mataram City.

Sampling Determination Technique

• Determination of sampling areas was carried out in three sub-districts in Mataram City, namely:

1. Pagesangan Timur Sub-district, Mataram District
2. Pejeluk Abian Sub-district, Ampenan District
3. Karang Taliwang Sub-district, Cakranegara District

These areas were selected by purposive sampling (informant selection intentionally) based on the number of beneficiaries of the P2L Program.

• Determination of informants using purposive sampling technique, with a total of 54 informants consisting of:

1. 18 people per group (3 groups from 3 sub-districts), which include:
 - 3 core administrators
 - 5 people from the management section
 - 10 group members
2. 3 key informants, namely:
 - Head of TP-PKK Mataram City
 - Coordinator of the Sub-district Agricultural Extension Center (BPP)
 - 1 group assistant (PPL).

Types and Sources of Data

- Primary Data: obtained directly from in-depth interviews and observations in the field.
- OSecondary Data: obtained from journals, books, reports, and documents from related agencies.

Data Collection Techniques

1. In-depth interviews using a structured questionnaire.
2. Direct observation to record various data needed.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using descriptive analysis methods, which aim to provide a systematic, factual, and accurate picture of the phenomenon being studied. This analysis does not generalize or infer, but rather explains the data as it is.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. General Conditions of the Research Area

Mataram City is the capital city of West Nusa Tenggara Province which has an area of around 61.3 km². This area consists of six sub-districts and 50 villages with a high population density. Based on 2023 data, the rate of land conversion in Mataram City continues to increase, causing a reduction in productive agricultural land. The Sustainable Food Yard (P2L) Program is one solution to maintaining food security and utilizing yard land for household-scale agriculture. Mataram City experienced significant land conversion with a land area of 1,381.84 ha in 2023, reducing the availability of land for agriculture. However, there is potential for the use of non-rice field land of 917.26 ha which can be utilized for the P2L program

B. Informant Characteristics

The informants in this study consisted of members of the Women Farmers Group (KWT) involved in the P2L Program in three sub-districts, namely Pagesangan Timur, Pejeruk Abian, and Karang Taliwang. The informants consisted of core group administrators, section members in the management, and general members. The age range of the informants ranged from 30 to 55 years with varying levels of education, from elementary school to college. Most of the informants had more than five years of farming experience and had attended various training related to yard farming.

C. Specific Description of the Groups that are the Study of the Implementation of the Sustainable Food Yard Program in Mataram City

The groups that are the focus of this study are KWT Patuh Karya, KWT Abian Ceria, and KWT Teratai Maju. Each group has received assistance in the form of facilities and infrastructure from the P2L program, including seed houses, demonstration plots, and agricultural tools. The implementation of this program is carried out using a participatory approach, where group members are directly involved in every stage of planning, implementation, and evaluation.

D. Implementation of the P2L Program in Mataram City

The implementation of the P2L program in Mataram City consists of several stages:

1. Socialization and Formation of Groups Socialization is carried out by the Agriculture Service together with field extension workers to increase public understanding of the benefits of P2L. Beneficiary groups are selected based on the criteria set out in the P2L Technical Instructions.
2. Provision of Facilities and Infrastructure Beneficiary groups receive assistance in the form of seed houses, vegetable and fruit seeds, agricultural tools, and other supporting facilities.
3. Management of Demonstration Plots and Members' Yards Each group has a demonstration plot that functions as a pilot area for cultivating horticultural crops. Group members are also encouraged to optimize their respective yards with vertical and hydroponic systems.
4. Mentoring and Monitoring Agricultural extension workers provide regular mentoring to ensure the success of the program. Evaluation is carried out through routine group meetings and progress reports submitted to the Agriculture Service.

E. Constraints in Implementing the P2L Program

Some of the constraints faced in implementing this program include:

- Limited Resources: Some groups face constraints in providing sustainable water and organic fertilizer.
- Lack of Member Participation: Not all group members have a high commitment to running the program, which affects the results achieved.
- Impact of Climate Change: Extreme weather such as high rainfall or drought has an impact on crop productivity.
- Lack of Harvest Marketing: Most of the harvest is only consumed by the group itself, while access to the market is still limited.

F. Evaluation Stage

Program evaluation is conducted by reviewing the effectiveness of each implementation stage. The evaluation results show that the P2L program in Mataram City has provided benefits in increasing household food availability, although there are still obstacles that need to be fixed. Efforts to strengthen group capacity, increase market access, and policy support from the government are key factors in the sustainability of this program.

IV. CONCLUSION

Conclusion:

Land conversion (conversion) in Mataram City is quite high in 2023, the land area will be 1,381.84 ha or there will be a land conversion of 96.42 ha. There is a potential area of non-rice fields of 917.26 ha. This non-rice field land includes various types of uses, including land yard with an average yard area of 10-30 m². P2L in Mataram City has been implemented well and provides real benefits for beneficiary groups. This program has succeeded in optimizing the use of yard land and increasing public awareness of the importance of independent food production, especially in increasing food security and household income. However, there are still obstacles in technical aspects, assistance, and limited resources that affect the effectiveness of implementation. Therefore, periodic evaluation, increased training, and more flexible policy support are needed so that this program can run more optimally and sustainably.

Suggestion:

To increase the success of the Sustainable Food Yard Program (P2L) in Mataram City, several strategic steps need to be taken, namely:

1. Program socialization must be expanded to reach more target groups and increase community participation.
2. Additional technical training for Women Farmers Groups (KWT) must be increased, especially in crop management, product marketing, and cultivation innovation.
3. Evaluation and revision of the Technical Instructions (Juknis) are carried out to be more adaptive to specific regional conditions.
4. Innovations that have been successfully implemented in several groups need to be replicated to other regions.
5. Cross-sector synergy with the government, community organizations, and educational institutions must be strengthened to increase the sustainability of the program.

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